

ChatGPT ing

Your participation in this survey will take approximately 3 minutes to complete. This questionnaire aims to identify the role of ChatGPT in higher education teaching. It investigates how ChatGPT is being utilized to enhance learning and knowledge production in higher education. The questions in this survey are intended for educators who have previously used ChatGPT for learning or knowledge production in higher education. Therefore, if you have used it, please assist us with the survey.

INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

By responding to this survey, you permit the researcher to obtain, use, and disclose the provided anonymous information as described below.

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be personally identified. I agree to complete the survey for research purposes and that data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences, and blog posts.
2. I understand that my participation in this survey is entirely voluntary and that refusal to participate will not result in any penalty or loss of benefits. I can withdraw my participation at any time if I wish. I also understand that if I choose to participate, I can refuse to answer any question I do not feel comfortable with.
3. I understand that I can contact the researcher if I have any questions about the survey. I am aware that my consent will not directly benefit me. I am also aware that the author will retain the collected data indefinitely and may use the data for future academic work.
4. By clicking the button below, I freely agree and acknowledge my rights as a voluntary participant in the survey as described above and grant consent to the researcher to use my information in conducting research in the mentioned areas.

* Obrigatória

Consent - Do you consent to participate in this survey?

1. Do you consent to participate in this survey?

Yes

No

2. . Email - Optional response

3. In which state do you currently live?

- Acre
- Alagoas
- Amapá
- Amazonas
- Bahia
- Ceará
- Distrito Federal
- Espírito Santo
- Goiás
- Maranhão
- Mato Grosso
- Mato Grosso do Sul
- Minas Gerais
- Pará
- Paraíba
- Paraná
- Pernambuco
- Piauí
- Rio de Janeiro
- Rio Grande do Norte

Rio Grande do Sul

Rondônia

Roraima

Santa Catarina

São Paulo

Sergipe

Tocantins

Outra

4. What is the nature of your work and/or organization?

Federal University

State University

Federal Institute

Private College

Private University

Private University Center

5. How long have you been working as a higher education professor? *

Less than one year

One to three years

Four to six years

Seven to nine years

Ten to fifteen

Over 16 years

6. What is your area of teaching? *

- Software Engineering
- Systems analysis
- Database
- Programming language
- Requirements engineering
- Artificial intelligence
- Computer network
- Data structure
- Distributed systems
- Software quality
- Other areas
- Outra

7. What is your educational background? *

- Graduate
- Postgraduate
- Master's student
- Master's degree
- Doctorate
- Doctoral student
- Postdoctoral

Use of ChatGPT

8. ChatGPT was made available in Nov/2022. For how many months have you been using ChatGPT?

- Less than 1
- Between 1 and 3 months
- Between 4 and 6 months
- More than 6 months

9. In my opinion, ChatGPT will have a significant impact on all areas of knowledge

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

10. In my opinion, ChatGPT will have a significant impact on education, especially in higher education.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

11. Have you already used any of these techniques in your teaching with ChatGPT?

- Create a chat room using GPT technology. Utilize existing chat tools like Discord or Slack to create a chat room using GPT.
- Train the GPT model. For GPT to be effective, it needs to be trained with data related to the subject matter. Training can be done using textbooks, articles, etc
- Use GPT to answer student questions: Once the GPT model is trained, it can be used to answer student questions in real-time.
- Customize the GPT model to adapt to the teaching style and preferences of the students. For instance, one can select a GPT model inclined towards practical examples or clarifying theoretical concepts
- Monitor the effectiveness of the GPT model in the chat room. Students should be asked to evaluate the quality of responses and how they aid in the learning process.
- Automatically generate a performance-based assessment task.
- Automatically assess responses written by students.
- Provide domain-specific questions and answers.
- Personalized support offering interactive assistance for self-directed learners.
- Extract and summarize student chat in a collaborative app to understand student collaboration in collaborative learning environments.
- Interactive exercises and games tailored to specific student learning needs.
- Self-assessment and reflection processes can help students take responsibility for their own learning and growth, as well as develop necessary skills and methods.
- Support in creating a course syllabus.
- Support in developing content to work with students
- Outra

12. Please cite the main results of the application of these techniques (positive or negative).

13. What other techniques have you used in your teaching? What were the results (positive and negative)?

14. Have you used any of these techniques when developing research, articles, or texts with ChatGPT?

- Assistance in writing a research paper or essay by providing the model with a thesis statement and key points.
- Literature review support: identifying literature, generating article summaries, or providing a list of relevant articles on a specific topic or keyword basis.
- Text generation: producing text in a specific style or tone, enabling the generation of preliminary versions of research papers and other written materials.
- Data analysis: analyzing large quantities of text data, such as social media posts or news articles, providing insights and identifying patterns.
- Automated summarization: automatically summarizing articles or other documents, making it easier for researchers to stay updated
- Answering questions: providing questions and answers in specific domains.
- Outra

15. In your perception, what are the main problems with using ChatGPT in higher education? Is there any way to mitigate them?

16. In your perception, what are the main advantages of using ChatGPT in higher education teaching?

17. In your perception, is there a need for training professors to be able to use ChatGPT in higher education more effectively? Why?

18. The use of ChatGPT in teaching will be permanent. It will be a new tool to be used in teaching and knowledge generation.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

19. Regarding the previous question, could you inform us why

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